

MULTI-MODE DAMAGE MODEL FOR STRUCTURES OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

This paper presents a multi-mode damage model for composite structures. The new model provides a means in which to predict the developments and the effects of both intra- and inter-laminar damage modes in structure made of laminated composites. The model is incorporated into finite element for structural response.

Keywords: Continuum damage mechanics, matrix cracking, delamination

INTRODUCTION

Failure of composite materials is a complex process due to the heterogeneity and anisotropy characteristics of composites. Based on the laminate construction and the loading conditions, it usually starts from an intra-laminar damage mode (fibre/matrix debonding, matrix cracking) and gradually develops to an inter-laminar damage mode (delamination); and if not controlled it will lead to an ultimate failure (fracture). Moreover, one damage mode is most likely to induce or to interact with another damage mode and therefore accelerates the damaging process.

Most of the current damage models are based on shear lag [1, 2], fracture mechanics [3], micromechanics [4], and continuum damage mechanics [5, 6]. These models are capable of predicting the extent of certain damage modes and therefore the life prediction of laminated composite. However, they seem to be restricted to certain laminate geometry (e.g. composite lay-up) and load history (e.g. monotonic or uniform load conditions). General application of composite involves complex geometry subject to local concentrations and combined loading conditions. Finite element packages are widely used to capture the stress and strain fields of laminated structures. Yet accurate damage model are required to be incorporated into the FE code to account for the degradation effects due to damage modes [7, 8].

To simulate the damage process, a multi-scale model, which takes into the account different damage modes, is required [9]. The proposed model in this paper incorporates Li's continuum damage model [6] in finite element to predict the development of matrix cracking and uses cohesive elements to measure the onset and extent of delamination. As an example of the application of the new model, the response of a composite tube subject to indentation is presented and the results are discussed.

INTRA-LAMINAR DAMAGE

At the lamina scale, the model is focused on matrix cracking as it is the first and most common damage mode in composite materials. Continuum damage mechanics is used to represent the damage state and the evolution of damage. The damage state for a lamina is represented by a damage parameter which is incorporated into the laminar constitutive equation to account for the degradation effects. The damage growth law is represented through the concept of damage surface with conventional failure criteria. The incremental form of the laminar constitutive equation is incorporated in ABAQUS via UMAT user-subroutine.

Continuum damage mechanics

Li's continuum model [6], which has been subject to extensive validation, takes into the account three sources of nonlinearity during the laminate analysis. These sources are plastic shear stress-strain relation, fibre reorientation and transverse matrix cracking. The nonlinear shear stress-strain response is assumed to be pseudo-plastic and the shear stress is a function of plastic shear strain as illustrated in Figure 1. Fibre orientation in a lamina may change relative to loading axis of the laminate due to large deformation. At the end of each increment, the current fibre orientation and laminar stiffness is updated to account for the fibre scissoring effects.

Figure 1: Nonlinear in-plan shear stress-strain curve

The effects of matrix cracking are represented by a damage parameter which is defined as the relative change in the transverse Young's modulus.

$$\omega = 1 - E_2 / E_2^0 \quad (1)$$

The stress-strain-damage relation in a lamina is given by

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_1^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} & \frac{\nu_{12}^0 E_2^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{12}^0 E_2^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} & \frac{E_2^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & kG_6 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0 E_1^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)^2} & -\frac{\nu_{12}^0 E_2^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)^2} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}^0 E_2^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)^2} & -\frac{E_2^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & kG_6 \end{bmatrix} \omega \quad (2)$$

Implementation in FE

The laminar constitutive relation is expressed in terms of stresses, strains and other solution dependent variables (the damage parameter and plastic shear strain) and then incorporated into ABAQUS via UMAT user-defined subroutine. UMAT is called at each material integration points to update the stresses, stiffness and the solution dependent variables. A flowchart of UMAT is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Flowchart of UMAT implementation in ABAQUS

INTER-LAMINAR DAMAGE

At the laminate scale, delamination damage mode is considered to be one of the typical and highly destructive interfacial damage modes in laminated composites. Delamination is likely to develop in an interface of two layers of different fibre orientations due to inter-laminar stresses. Delamination is usually modelled following the concepts of fracture mechanics [10]. However, micromechanics is usually used first to predict the onset of delamination and then the fracture mechanics is used to predict its propagation. Cohesive elements provide suitable mean to model the rich-resin bond interfaces between layers as an interface layer with zero or small thickness and a large stiffness [11]. By defining the interface constitutive response of cohesive elements directly in terms of traction versus separation, the initiation of delamination can be predicted along with its propagation. The stiffness of the cohesive zone is gradually degraded as the damage zone continues to grow.

APPLICATION

The problem of laminated composite structure subject to lateral impact is essential in testing damage model because of the generality in stress state and the development possibility of different damage modes. There has been enormous work over decades for the prediction of deformation and damage development in filament-wound tube subject to quasi-static indentation [12-14].

A cylindrical laminated tube with a nominal thickness of 1 mm, diameter of 100 mm and 500 mm long is modelled as 2-cover of ± 55 filament-wound tube. The tube is supported at the bottom by a flat analytical rigid plate and the indentation is applied by a rigid hemisphere of 50 mm diameter at the top centre of the tube with prescribed displacement load. The tube is made of 4-noded shell elements reduced integration (S4R) and frictionless contact condition where used between the Tube and both the indenter and plate. The initial material properties of E-glass fibre reinforced epoxy resin for unidirectional ply are shown in Table 1 and FE model is shown in Figure 3.

The introduction of an interface layer of cohesive elements provides a mechanism which allows a delamination to emerge at the interface due to the inter-laminar stresses. The inclusion of cohesive elements in the model is work on progress. Nevertheless, the full results will be present in the conference.

Table 1: Mechanical material properties of GRE ply

Longitudinal Young's modulus	$E_L = 45.6 \text{ GPa}$
Transverse Young's modulus	$E_T = 16.23 \text{ GPa}$
Longitudinal shear stress–strain relationship	
Linear section	$G_L = 5.5 \text{ GPa}$ for $\gamma \leq 0.00651$
Nonlinear section	$\tau(\text{MPa}) = 0.031 + 7.2584 \times 10^3 \gamma - 309.66 \times 10^3 \gamma^2$ $+ 6.281 \times 10^6 \gamma^3 - 48.4 \times 10^6 \gamma^4$ for $0.00651 < \gamma < 0.04$
Extrapolated section	$\tau(\text{MPa}) = 73 + 244(\gamma - 0.04)$ for $\gamma \geq 0.04$
Transverse shear modulus	$G_T = 5.5 \text{ GPa}$
Longitudinal Poisson's ratio	$\nu_T = 0.278$
Longitudinal tensile strength	$\sigma_{Lt}^* = 1280 \text{ MPa}$
Longitudinal compressive strength	$\sigma_{Lc}^* = 525 \text{ MPa}$
Transverse tensile strength	$\sigma_{Tt}^* = 40 \text{ MPa}$
Transverse compressive strength	$\sigma_{Tc}^* = 145 \text{ MPa}$
Longitudinal shear strength	$\tau^* = 73 \text{ MPa}$
Thermal expansion coefficient	$\alpha_L = 8.6 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\alpha_T = 26.4 \times 10^{-6}$

Figure 3: Finite element model of composite tube

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the indentation problem are presented below in global and local area. In the global structure area, the overall response of the composite tube is determined from the load-displacement relation during the indentation. The intensity and extent of the damage zone is present in the local areas, especially immediately under the indenter, where extensive damage was observed.

Load-displacement relation during the indentation

The tube was loaded through the displacement of the indenter until the analysis was aborted. The predicted load-displacement curve by FE is shown in Figure 4 along with the experimental curve. Both curves follow bilinear trends due to the effects of damage and shear nonlinearity, although the FE predicts slightly higher load than the experiment. Moreover, the FE curve shows couple knees after 40 mm indentation which correspond to abrupt reduction in the stiffness due to the application of ply-discount for failure modes other than matrix cracking (fibre failure, shear failure and compressive matrix failure). While the final failure of experiment was recorded at 48.2 mm, the FE analysis aborted at an indentation load of 46.7 mm due to the singularity in the stiffness matrix. In the experiment, the final failure did not occurred under the indenter but at 30°-50° around the circumference away from the point of indentation. This failure is related to the local buckling caused by high in-plane axial compression. This failure zone was also captured in the FE model as showing in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Comparison of the modelling and experimental load versus indentation curve

Figure 5: Compressive matrix failure mode of the composite tube and top view of the indentation zone for each layer (failed elements indicated by red colour)

Development of Damage

The area right under the indenter is of interest as it involves the highest stresses and the most severe damage developments. In-plane stresses and therefore damage and plastic shear strains are different from one layer to another due to the biaxial bending effects. The top layer is mainly under compression, whereas the bottom layer is under tension. The tensile stresses cause matrix cracking and therefore higher value of damage parameter. Contour plots of damage parameter for the area immediately under the indenter are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 6: Top view of the predicted damage zone immediately under the indenter, the legend is for the value damage parameter (0-undamage, 1-complete failure)

Damage in terms of matrix cracking starts to develop in the innermost layer first and then propagates gradually through the thickness direction. At the end of the indentation, the innermost layer shows significant damage development.

CONCLUSIONS

A continuum damage mechanics for matrix cracking was successfully incorporated in FE code for structural analysis via UMAT user subroutine. The model has been applied to the problem of filament-wound GRE tube subject to lateral indentation. The global load-displacement response of the composite tube and damage development in the local area under the indenter were presented and discussed.

The overall trend of experimental results has been predicted fairly well in the modelling. The application of ply discount which causes the abrupt and significant reduction in tube stiffness is responsible for the small discrepancies in the results.

The model brings the analysis of matrix cracking and delamination together as both exists in practical application of laminated composites. The in situ interactions between the two modes of damage have not been addressed yet, but will be pursued in the future.

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